

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF TOLERANT ATTITUDE OF FATHER AND MOTHER TO SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *In the family today the task of forming the values of tolerance and religious tolerance in children`s thinking is one of the most urgent, social and theoretical problems facing the direction of pedagogy and pedagogy. Tolerance is one of the most important features of a secular state.*

Keywords: *tolerance, parents, family, pedagogue, thinking, education, compromise.*

The person is formed first of all from the family. The process of forming the mindset of tolerance in the family has been nurtured since ancient times, preserved through the Islamic spirituality in the Middle Ages, and later Uzbek enlighteners added modern content to it, and it is being preserved and improved to this day. What is tolerance? TOLERANCE (lat. tolerantia - patience), tolerance - tolerance for the way of life, behavior, habits, feelings, opinions, ideas and beliefs of others. It should be noted that there are more than 160 nationalities and peoples in Uzbekistan. Sometimes children of 3-4 nationalities are educated in one preschool educational institution. They come from different families, representatives of different cultures, and have their own values and methods of education. The process of working with parents is important in raising children of such families and representatives of multinational families in groups. A lot of work on working with parents is done by the educator - pedagogue, because he sees the changes taking place in the upbringing of the child more than anyone else and is closely familiar with the children's life. He advises parents on what to pay more attention to in raising children, preparing them for school education, taking care of their health, properly organizing their food and daily routine, etc.

Everyone has different development opportunities. Many people mistake good manners for good education. The child's feelings should not be disturbed. Children's thinking should be matched with compassion for people and their problems. For this, it is important to establish a wider cooperation between educators and parents in the preschool education organization.

Collaboration is communication on "equal terms" where no one has the privilege of directing, directing, or evaluating. We must not forget that a child is a unique person. For this reason, it is absolutely impossible for us to compare him with other children, equate him and accept him as a judge. There is no one like him in the world and we must support and develop him while taking into account his young nature. The team of educators and parents should actively participate in the establishment of cooperation between the kindergarten and the family. Only then can the expected results in child education be achieved. Here are the most common forms and methods of cooperation of kindergarten employees with parents and families:

-one-on-one work with parents and families. This includes visits of the tutor to the family, conducting an interview for the parents, giving them advice, introducing the parents to the life of the child in the preschool educational institutions.

- activities that are organized and applied on a permanent basis with parents in a team style. These are group and general meetings of parents, school of parents, conferences, Saturdays, question-and-answer nights.

- such types of instructional work, organization of exhibitions, demonstration of children's works, open day, parents' corner, organization of libraries for parents.

- Visiting the child's family and getting to know his family members.

The peculiarity of the Uzbek family is the oriental manners, customs, traditions, national values and traditions, education and upbringing, and a homely family that creates the basis for striving for spiritual maturity. Our children are above all in the survival of others. Children's education and learning is formed mainly in the family, following the example of their parents.

If the parents diligently inculcate in the child the qualities of education, speech culture, and humanity, then in the future he will grow up to be a mature, healthy, independent thinker, and most importantly, a decent person.

A person learns the culture of seeking knowledge, loving and honoring the Motherland, respecting elders, and behavior from parents. There are various ways and means of providing spiritual, moral, and cultural education to the young generation, among which children's speech and behavior have a special place. A child is the happiness and wealth of parents. In turn, he respects his parents diligently, which is considered a family trait.

Each family is formed based on the requirements of the community. The development of the society directly depends on the level of formation of the socio-economic and spiritual image of the families in it. Family relationships not only ensure children's mental and spiritual maturity, but also create a unique activity in parents. A healthy spiritual and spiritual environment in the family is of incomparable importance for children to grow up mature and mature.

The new concept of interaction between the family and the pre-school educational organization is based on the idea that parents are responsible for raising their children, and all other social institutions are responsible for helping them in their educational activities. intended to support, guide and complement.

The policy of transferring education from the family to the public education system, which is officially implemented in our country, is becoming a thing of the past. Recognizing the primacy of family education requires a new family-to-school relationship. The novelty of this relationship is determined by the concepts of "cooperation" and "interaction".

There is no unity in the understanding of tolerance in society. People have different ideas about what tolerance is and what its limits are. According to one view, tolerance is a property of a person, according to another, it is a behavioral skill. Being in social formations such as "family", "school", "class", "village", "city", "country" is not so easy. The object of intolerance in children's environment can be national, ethnic, gender, social, religious affiliation, appearance features, habits, hobbies. The child imitates what he sees. As a child, he still cannot distinguish between good and evil. It is not yet clear to him who he is and how he behaves in different situations. The child is looking for ways to assert himself: "I must be afraid, I must be strong."

Cultivating in children an infinite respect for their parents, who gave them life and spent a lot of mental and physical effort to make them grow up and be happy. Taking into account the wishes and suggestions of parents, ensuring their participation in the life of the group and being able to put it on the right track, it is important for us to solve the main problem today.

At what age does tolerance develop? From early childhood, a child learns certain norms that force him to do good or bad. Almost from the first months, he divides people into friends and enemies. How are the moral relations that determine the concepts of "own" and "other" formed? a three-month-old baby clearly prefers people of his own race and is afraid of people with obvious characteristics of another race. The concept of "I" is formed in it. Three-year-old children, without hesitation, only support themselves, without trying to understand the situation, enter into relationships with those they consider close or equal. Out of fear, they refuse to play games and communicate with unfamiliar and unfamiliar peers. At the age of five, children understand very well who is the aggressor and the victim in this situation, who should be pitied and supported, and who should be punished.

Xulosa: Ushbu davrda boshqa insonlarga nisbatan bag'rikenglik ko'rsatish zarurati, tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Falsafada "tolerantlik" tushunchasiga bir necha yondashuvlar mavjud. Bizga eng yaqin bo'lgan narsa – bu tolerantlikni tanqidiy muloqot natijasida pozitsiyalarni o'zaro o'zgartirishga munosabat bilan birgalikda, birovning pozitsiyasiga hurmat sifatida tushunish. Bunga imkon beradigan vaziyatlarda murosa topish. Ijtimoiy ma'noda bag'rikenglik dunyo madaniyatlarining eng boy xilma-xilligini hurmat qilish, qabul qilish va to'g'ri tushunishni, o'zimizni ifodalash shakllarini va insonning individualligini ifoda etish usullarini anglatadi. Tolerantlikning asosi – boshqacha bo'lish huquqini tan olishdir. Jamiyatga bag'rikenglik g'oyalari va tamoyillarini joriy etish uchun mas'uliyat, asosan, pedagogika zimmasiga yuklanadi. Tolerantlikni shakllantirish juda uzoq jarayon va menimcha, uni imkon qadar erta boshlash kerak. Ayniqsa maktabgacha yoshda, bag'rikenglikni shakllantirish bo'yicha ishlarni boshlash uchun barcha zarur sharoitlar paydo bo'ladi. O'zboshimchalik bilan xatti-harakatlar, motivlarning bo'ysunishi, hissiy kutish qobiliyati kabi shaxsiy neoplazmalar mavjud; rivojlanishning ijtimoiy holati o'zgaradi; bola odamlarning munosabatlariga, ularning ijtimoiy pozitsiyalariga, ijtimoiy funksiyalariga jalb qilina boshlaydi. Voyaga yetgan odam, namuna sifatida ajralib turadi, shuning uchun bag'rikenglikni shakllantirishda unga katta mas'uliyat yuklanadi. Kattalarning o'zlari shaxsiy namuna orqali bag'rikenglik munosabatini ko'rsatishi va buni xatti-harakatlarida ko'rsatishi kerak. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda bag'rikenglikni rivojlantirish jarayoniga pedagoglar va ota-onalarning maqsadli jalb etilishi ularning pedagogik pozitsiyasini faollashtirishga imkon beradi va kattalar tomonidan o'zlarining baholash munosabatlari va xatti-harakatlarini qayta ko'rib chiqishga yordam beradi.

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